

The Use of Offline Game-Based Intervention Material in Reading English for Intermediate Frustration Level Readers in the New Normal

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Abstract:-

➤ Purpose

This study aimed to determine the learners' reading skills before and after using the offline game-based intervention to Frustration Level Readers of San Jose Elementary School.

➤ Design/Methodology/Approach

The study utilized experimental research and purposive sampling technique was administered. Phil-IRI was conducted to identify the pre-test and post-test results through home visitation. Frequency, percentage and T-test were used to treat the data statistically.

➤ Findings

The result show that the respondents were all in Frustration Level before the implementation of the offline game-based intervention. Respondents showed progress in word recognition and reading comprehension after the implementation of the intervention. The t-value is 6.86 while the p-value is 0.001. There is a significant difference between the mean pre-test and post-test scores of the subjects of the study.

➤ Research Limitations/Implications

The study is limited to 52 out of 68 San Jose Elementary School intermediate level learners who fell under Frustration Level upon the implementation of Phil-IRI English category (pre-test), and limited to learners with smartphones only to be able to participate in this study.

➤ Originality/Value

This study integrated the use of Most Essential Competencies in offline game-based reading intervention which is unique among other electronic game-based activities for learners. The text-to-speech passages made the offline game-based reading intervention more interactive.

Keywords:- Offline Game; Text-To-Speech; Intervention; Frustration Level, Word Recognition, Reading Comprehension.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reading proficiency is essential for a wide variety of human activities. Considering its importance, reading was the main subject assessed in PISA 2018 (Programme for International Student Assessment 2018). The Philippines rank 41st out of 41 countries around the globe of said reading assessment. It agrees with the findings of Department of Education as it conduct its national assessment. Under DepEd Memo. No. 173, S. 2019, states that there are still early grade learners struggling to meet the learning standards in early language, literacy and numeracy. Low achievement level in English, Math, and Science appear to be caused by the gaps in learners' reading comprehension.

Meanwhile, DepEd Order Number 70, series of 2021 introduce Every Child A Reader Program to address the thrust of the Department of Education to make every child a reader at his/her own grade level. In support of the said program San Jose Elementary School utilized the use of game-based intervention material to Frustration Level Readers of the said school. The nature of the said intervention was digitalized downloadable interactive games from the internet, it was free and offline games. The composition was more on text-to-speech games for word recognition and leveled game passages for reading comprehension. The researcher believed that the said material is beneficial to both learners and teachers of the said school/district in teaching and learning reading English language in intermediate level learners.

A. Research Questions

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following queries:

- What is the level of reading ability of the students in English based on pre-test results using the Phil-IRI results in terms of Word Reading and Comprehension?
- What is the level of reading ability of the participants in Reading English after the implementation of the game-based intervention based on post-test results in terms of Word Reading and Reading Comprehension?
- Is there a significant difference in the reading skill of the participants based on the pre-test and post-test results?

B. Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test score of the respondents.

➤ *Brief Review of Related Literature and Studies*

Garnett (2011) states that oral word reading is the procedure of decoding a word and identifying its enunciation directly and without any cognizant struggle. If reading words entails mindful, effortful decoding, diminutive consideration is left for comprehension of a text to occur. Similarly, word recognition reading comprehension are the areas of reading (Chavez et al., 2014).

Reading comprehension is one of the most complex behaviors in which humans engage. Reading theorists have grappled with how to comprehensively and meaningfully portray reading comprehension and many different theoretical models have been proposed in recent decades (McNamara & Magliano, 2009; Perfetti & Stafura, 2014). On the other hand, Murray (2016) states that the ability to read words (word recognition) and understand those words (language comprehension) lead to skillful comprehension. Handheld devices are powerful learning tools for producing and sustaining improved student performance (Gulchak, 2008). The use of iPods in an 8th grade literature class, found that students developed deeper understanding of the concepts taught, were actively engaged and happy (Bauleke & Herrmann, 2010).

➤ *Scope and Limitations*

The action research is limited to 52 out of 68 San Jose Elementary School intermediate level learners who fell under Frustration Level upon the implementation of Phil-IRI English Category (pre-test), and limited to those learners with smartphones only to be able to participate in this study.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The research design was Experimental, one-group pre-test post-test design to be specific.

B. Participants

Originally there were 68 respondents but only 52 of them meet the requirement of being involve of the said intervention.

C. Sampling

Purposive sampling was administered to the concerned population.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI; English Category) was administered to determine the pre-test and post-test result of the respondents. After the pre-test, the intervention took place and the implementation of post-test was implemented. The data for both assessments were compared to see if there was a significant difference on the respondents' word-reading skills.

E. Data Analysis

For the statement of the problem 1 and 2, Frequency and Percentage was used. For statement of the problem number 3, T-test was utilized.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher made a table to comprehensively present the findings/results to each objective.

Table 1 Results for Word Recognition and Reading Comprehension Before Implementing Offline Game-Based Intervention

Grade Level	Frustration Level Readers			
	Word Recognition		Comprehension	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Grade IV	11	100%	11	100%
Grade V	21	100%	21	100%
Grade VI	20	100%	20	100%

Table 1 Shows that eleven (11) learners of Grade IV were all in frustration level when it comes to word recognition before the implementation of offline game-based intervention. Similarly, twenty-one (21) Grade V learners and twenty (20) Grade VI learners were also in the frustration level before the conduct of the Offline Game-Based Reading Intervention. It only implies that these learners have poor reading skills in the areas of word recognition skills before using offline game-based reading intervention.

Likewise, the table shows that eleven (11) learners of Grade IV were all in frustration level when it comes to reading comprehension before the implementation of offline game-based intervention. Similarly, twenty-one (21) Grade V learners and twenty (20) Grade VI learners were also in the frustration level before the conduct of the game-based intervention. It implies that the respondents have poor comprehension skills before the conduct of the game-based intervention.

Table 2 Results on Word Recognition and Reading Comprehension After Implementing Offline Game-Based Intervention

Grade Level	Word Recognition						Reading Comprehension					
	Frustration Level Readers		Instructional Level Readers		Independent Level Readers		Frustration Level Readers		Instructional Level Readers		Independent Level Readers	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Grade IV	1	9.1%	9	81.8%	1	9.1%	3	27.3%	3	27.3%	5	45.5%
Grade V	3	14.3%	18	85.7%	0	0%	6	28.6%	8	38.1%	7	33.3%
Grade VI	5	25.0%	15	75.0%	0	0%	3	15%	10	50%	7	35%

Table 2 shows that the 11 Frustration Level learners of Grade IV in beginning of the research in the area of word recognition fell into 1 Frustration Level learner, 9 Instructional Level learners, and 1 Independent Level learner, after administering the said intervention. The 21 Frustration Level learners of Grade V in the beginning of the research fell into 3 Frustration Level learners and 18 Instructional Level learners. Similarly, the 20 Frustration Level learners of Grade VI in beginning of the research fell into 5 Frustration Level learners and 15 Instructional Level learners. This result matches with the findings of the several studies that personal devices can help develop organizational skills, independent and active learning, and self-directed learning (Chavez, 2013).

It also illustrates that the 11 Frustration Level learners of Grade IV in beginning of the research that fell into 3 Frustration Level learners, 3 Instructional Level learners, and 5 Independent Level learners after the intervention. The group of 21 Frustration Level learners of Grade V in beginning of the research fell into 6 Frustration Level learners, 8 Instructional Level learners, and 7 Independent Level learners, after administering the intervention. Similarly, 20 Frustration Level learners in beginning of the research fell into 3 Frustration Level learner, 10 Instructional Level learners, and 7 Independent Level learner, after administering the intervention significant improvement is displayed by the respondents. The research is certain that the exposure of the respondents in the game-based instruction arouse their motivation and love for reading.

Table 3 Results on Word Recognition and Reading Comprehension Based on the Pre and Post Test

Word Recognition	Mean			T _c	P-Value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
	Pre	Post	Mean Difference				
Word Recognition	84.96	90.58	5.62	6.86	0.001	Reject	Significant
Reading Comprehension	39.31	70.96	31.85	11.24	0.001	Reject	Significant

Table 3 shows that the mean pre-test score and mean post-test score of the intermediate learners in word recognition is 84.96 and 90.58 respectively with a mean difference of 5.62. The t-value is 6.86 while the p-value is 0.001. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is significant difference between the mean pre-test and post-test scores of the subjects of the study. This result, implies that the inclusion of MELCs in the implementation of the offline game-based intervention, the performance of the intermediate learners in word recognition improved. The researcher is certain that the gadgets in the implementation of the intervention is a sustainable tool to adopt, and continuous utilization is needed.

It also shows that the mean pre-test score and mean post-test score of the intermediate learners in reading comprehension is 39.11 and 70.96 respectively with a mean difference of 31.85. The t-value is 11.24 while the p-value is 0.001. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is significant difference between the mean pre-test and post-

test scores of the subjects of the study. The impact of the intervention in the respondent is positive, indeed, it shows a high difference after implementing the intervention.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The research found out that the level of the respondents reading skills in word recognition and reading comprehension was in the frustration level before the implementation of the offline game-based intervention.

The respondents show progress in word recognition and reading comprehension after the implementation of the said intervention.

A significant difference was displayed by the respondent upon comparing the results of their pre-test and post-test, it resulted to a certain increase in respondents' word recognition and reading comprehension skill.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Facilitators who will implement Offline Game-Based Intervention might consider knowing their students' reading practices inside and outside the school before implementing the offline game-based intervention. Both environments can affect the learning of students in the areas reading (word recognition and reading comprehension).

The students' word recognition and reading comprehension will be more enhanced if the time allotted for this research is longer. Implementing the said treatment tool in the beginning of the academic year until it ends will result to a more enhanced reading skill.

REFERENCES

- [1]. DepEd Memo. No. 173, S. 2019. Hamon Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs Initiative) Retrieved at <http://www.deped.gov.ph>
- [2]. DepEd Memo. No. 70, S. 2011. Guidelines on the Utilization of Fund of Every Child A Reader Program (ECARP) Retrieved at <http://www.deped.gov.ph>
- [3]. Hanover R. (2016) Early Skills and Predictors of Academic Success. Arlington, VA: Author. Retrieved from <http://www.books.google.com.ph>
- [4]. Hess (2014). Digital Media and Student Learning: Impact of Electronic Books on Motivation and Achievement. Retrieved at http://scholar.google.com.ph/scholar?cluster=15494896502043386008&hl=en&as_sdt=2005&sciodt=0,5
- [5]. PISA Results (2018). Combined Executive Summaries.; Volume I, II, III. Retrieved from <http://www.oecd.org>